

"Big data Trends in 2020"

**International Journal of Computer Science &
Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

DEVELOPING AN INTEGRATED FRAMEWORK TO UTILIZE BIG DATA FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN SAUDI ARABIA

Noura A. Alsheikh

Information Management Department, Al Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University
(IMSIU), Saudi Arabia.

ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been widespread use of the Internet, the Internet of things, mobile devices, networks, and applications. All this usage produces daily huge data that cannot be processed using existing database management techniques and tools because of the size, the volume, the heterogeneity, and the unstructured nature of the data. This has led many sectors like healthcare, business, education, and so forth to start using Big Data technologies to analyze, process, decision making and performance. Big Data is “datasets which could not be captured, managed, and processed by general computers within an acceptable scope” [1]. Education sectors are one of the most important sectors that use information and communication technology (ICT). However, the education sector in Saudi Arabia is still behind other developed countries in terms of the adopting and implementation of Big Data techniques. The aim of this study is to develop an integrated framework to utilize Big Data for higher educational institutes in Saudi Arabia and to support decision making and improve performance. While many studies look at data mining and Big Data in the education sector, there are few studies that touch on this issue in Saudi education, especially in universities. The study collected data through self-administered surveys as a principal quantitative method and through semi structured in depth interviews as the follow-up qualitative method. The study used SPSS software to analyze the data from surveys and used manual analysis to analyze the interview data. This study’s major contribution addresses issues related to the development of a research framework that presents factors affecting the adoption and implementation of Big Data.

KEYWORDS

Big data, education, data mining, Saudi Arabia, Riyadh, factors, adoption.

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/abstract/ijcsit/v11n1/11119ijcsit03.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Singh, M. and Kumar G, D. [Effective Big Data Management and Opportunities for Implementation](#). United States of America by: Information Science Reference, N.d.
- [2] G. Picciano, —[The evolution of Big Data and learning analytics in American higher education](#),” Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks, vol. 16, pp. 9-20, 2012.
- [3] T. Poleto, V. D. H. De Carvalho, and A. P. C. Seixas Costa, The roles of Big Data in the decision-support process: An empirical investigation,” Lecture Notes in Business, pp. 10-21, 2015.
- [4] Mukthar and M. Sultan, —Big Data analytics for higher education in Saudi Arabia,” International Journal Of Computer Science And Information Security, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 3–22, 2017.
- [5] Deepa and E. C. Blessie, —[Big Data analytics for accreditation in the higher education sector](#),” International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 357–360, 2017.
- [6] Hussain and M. Safdar, —[Role of information technologies in teaching learning process: perception of the faculty](#),” Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE, vol. X, pp. 46–56, April 2008.
- [7] F. Hamidi, M. Meshkat, M. Rezaee, and M. Jafari, Information technology in education,” In Procedia Computer Science (Vol. 3), Netherlands: Elsevier Ltd, 2011.
- [8] Ryann K. Ellis, A Field Guide to Learning Management Systems. American Society for Training and Development (ASTD), 2009.
- [9] Letouzé, —United Nations Global Pulse, | Unglobalpulse.org, Big Data for Development: Opportunities & Challenges, 2012.
- [10] W. Pan, Q. Yang, C. Aggarwal, and C. Koch, —Big Data,” IEEE Intelligent Systems, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 7–8, 2017. doi: 10.1109/mis.2017.32.
- [11] P. Zikopoulos, C. Eaton, D. deRoos, T. Deutsch, and G. Lapis, Understanding Big Data Analytics for Enterprise Class Hadoop and Streaming Data, New York: McGraw-Hill, 2011.
- [12] L. Hbib and H. Barka, Big data: Framework and issues. In 2016 International Conference on Electrical and Information Technologies (ICEIT) pp. 485–490, 2016.
- [13] S. Petter, W. DeLone, and E. McLean, —[Measuring information systems success: Models, dimensions, measures, and interrelationships](#),” European Journal of Information Systems, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 236–263, 2008.

- [14] T. Oliveira and M. Martins, —[Literature review of information technology adoption models at firm level](#),” Electronic Journal of Information, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 110–121, 2011.
- [15] L. Tornatzky, M. Fleischer, and A. Chakrabarti, —[The Processes of Technological Innovation](#),|| Lexington, Mass.: Lexington, 1990.
- [16] Drigas, and P. Leliopoulos, —[The use of Big Data in education](#),”International Journal of Computer Science Issues, vol. 11 no. 5, pp. 58–63, 2014.
- [17] B. Tulasi and R. Suchithra, —[Big Data analytics and E learning in higher education](#),” International Journal on Cybernetics & Informatics, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 81–85, 2016. doi: 10.5121/ijci.2016.5108
- [18] B. Daniel, (2014). —[Big Data and analytics in higher education: Opportunities and challenges](#),” British Journal of Educational Technology, vol. 46, pp. 1–10, 2014.
- [19] M. Saunders, P. Lewis, and A. Thornhill, Research Methods for Business Students, Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall, 2012.
- [20] V. Sarala, and J. Krishnaiah, —[Empirical Study Of Data Mining Techniques In Education System](#),” International Journal of Advances in Computer Science and Technology (IJACST), vol.4, pp. 15–21,2015.
- [21] P. Veeramuthu, D. R. Periyasamy, and V. Sugasini, [Analysis of Student Result Using Clustering Techniques](#),”International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, pp. 5092–5094, 2014.
- [22] S. Suganya and V. Narayani, —[Analysis of students dropout forecasting using data mining](#),” In 3rd International Conference on Latest Trends in Engineering, Science, Humanities and Management, 2017.

BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert

Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York

ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N4/11419ijcsit04.pdf>

REFERENCES

- [1] Konstantinou, I., Angelou, E., Boumpouka, C., Tsoumakos, D., & Koziris, N. (2011, October). [On the elasticity of nosql databases over cloud management platforms](#). In Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management (pp. 2385-2388). ACM.
- [2] Labrinidis, Alexandros, and Hosagrahar V. Jagadish. "[Challenges and opportunities with big data](#)." Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment 5.12 (2012): 2032-2033.
- [3] Abadi, D. J. (2009). Data management in the cloud: Limitations and opportunities. IEEE Data Eng. Bull, 32(1), 3-12.
- [4] Luhn, H. P. (1958). A business intelligence system. IBM Journal of Research and Development, 2(4), 314-319 International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT) Vol 11, No 4, August 2019 57
- [5] Sivarajah, Uthayasankar, et al. "[Critical analysis of Big Data challenges and analytical methods](#)." Journal of Business Research 70 (2017): 263-286.
- [6] <https://www.bmc.com/blogs/saas-vs-paas-vs-iaas-whats-the-difference-and-how-to-choose/>
- [7] Kavis, Michael J. Architecting the cloud: design decisions for cloud computing service models (SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS). John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [8] https://www.ripublication.com/ijaer17/ijaerv12n17_89.pdf
- [9] Sakr, S. & Gaber, M.M., 2014. Large Scale and big data: Processing and Management Auerbach, ed.
- [10] Ji, Changqing, et al. "Big data processing in cloud computing environments." 2012 12th international symposium on pervasive systems, algorithms and networks. IEEE, 2012.
- [11] Han, J., Haihong, E., Le, G., & Du, J. (2011, October). Survey on nosql database. In Pervasive Computing and Applications (ICPCA), 2011 6th International Conference on (pp. 363-366). IEEE.
- [12] Zhang, L. et al., 2013. Moving big data to the cloud. INFOCOM, 2013 Proceedings IEEE, pp.405–409
- [13] Fernández, Alberto, et al. "[Big Data with Cloud Computing: an insight on the computing environment, MapReduce, and programming frameworks](#)." Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 4.5 (2014): 380-409.
- [14] http://acme.able.cs.cmu.edu/pubs/uploads/pdf/IoTBD_2016_10.pdf
- [15] Xiaofeng, Meng, and Chi Xiang. "[Big data management: concepts, techniques and challenges \[J\]](#)." Journal of computer research and development 1.98 (2013): 146-169.
- [16] Muniswamaiah, Manoj & Agerwala, Tilak & Tappert, Charles. (2019). [Challenges of Big Data Applications in Cloud Computing](#). 221-232. 10.5121/csit.2019.90918.

QUERY OPTIMIZATION FOR BIG DATA ANALYTICS

Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert

Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York

ABSTRACT

Organizations adopt different databases for big data which is huge in volume and have different data models. Querying big data is challenging yet crucial for any business. The data warehouses traditionally built with On-line Transaction Processing (OLTP) centric technologies must be modernized to scale to the ever-growing demand of data. With rapid change in requirements it is important to have near real time response from the big data gathered so that business decisions needed to address new challenges can be made in a timely manner. The main focus of our research is to improve the performance of query execution for big data.

KEYWORDS

Databases, Big data, Optimization, Analytical Query, Data Analysts and Data Scientists

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N5/11519ijcsit06.pdf>

REFERENCES

- [1] Duggan, J., Elmore, A. J., Stonebraker, M., Balazinska, M., Howe, B., Kepner, J., et al. (2015). The BigDAWG Polystore System. *ACM Sigmod Record*, 44(3)
- [2] V. Srinivasan and M. Carey. Performance of B-Tree Concurrency Control Algorithms. In *Proc.ACM SIGMOD Conf.*, pages 416–425, 1991
- [3] A. Elmore, J. Duggan, M. Stonebraker, M. Balazinska, U. Cetintemel, V. Gadepally, J. Heer, B. Howe, J. Kepner, T. Kraska et al., “A demonstration of the bigdawg polystore system,” *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1908–1911, 2015
- [4] <http://kylin.apache.org>
- [5] D. Halperin et al. Demonstration of the myria big data management service. In *SIGMOD*, pages 881–884, 2014.
- [6] Fuad, A., Erwin, A. and Ipung, H.P., 2014, September. Processing performance on Apache Pig, Apache Hive and MySQL cluster. In *Information, Communication Technology and System (ICTS), 2014 International Conference on* (pp. 297-302). IEEE.
- [7] Liu, Shaosu, et al. "Kodiak: leveraging materialized views for very low-latency analytics over high-dimensional web-scale data." *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment* 9.13 (2016): 1269-1280
- [8] <https://lens.apache.org/>
- [9] <https://calcite.apache.org/>
- [10] Muniswamaiah, Manoj & Agerwala, Tilak & Tappert, Charles. (2019). Query Performance Optimization in Databases for Big Data. 85-90. 10.5121/csit.2019.90908.
- [11] <https://www1.nyc.gov/site/tlc/about/tlc-trip-record-data.page>
- [12] Luke Welling, Laura Thomson, *PHP and MySQL Web Development*, Sams, Indianapolis, IN, 2001
- [13] <https://www.splicemachine.com/>
- [14] C. Bear, A. Lamb, and N. Tran. The vertica database: Sql rdbms for managing big data. In *Proceedings of the 2012 workshop on Management of big data systems*, pages 37–38. ACM, 2012
- [15] Cong Jin, Shuang Ran, "The research for storage scheme based on Hadoop", *Computer and Communications (ICCC) 2015 IEEE International Conference on*, pp. 62-66, 2015.